

SINGLE FIBRE PULL-OUT TEST FOR THE MATERIAL SELECTION OF A HYBRID RESIN COMPOSITE

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ABSTRACT

Fibre-resin-interface is an important composite parameter for the mechanical properties of fibre-reinforced plastics. An insufficient interface between fibres and resin leads to early debonding between both materials and therefore premature failure in the overall composite. Moreover, the interface characteristic is essentially driven by the fibre sizing. Here, several fibre sizings exist for carbon fibres, which are just suitable either for thermosets or for thermoplastics. It is becoming exciting, when a thermoset as well as a thermoplastic is implemented in one common composite and an additional carbon fibre woven fabric lays in between both resin system. Then, a trade-off regarding the carbon fibre including the fibre sizing need to be done to optimize the hybrid composite system.

In an experimental testing study, the fibre-pull-out test was used to make a statement regarding the interface properties of different fibres and resin systems, especially thermoplastics like PEI, PVDF and PA6. Here, the testing devices, FIMABOND and FAVIMAT+, were used to realize the tests. To evaluate the ideal fibre embedding conditions, rheological tests were done with the thermoplastics. Furthermore, the tensile strength of the fibre material should be known, because it can influence the embedding depth. Some embedded fibres were scanned by an x-ray microscope to ensure the quality of the specimens and to optimize the embedding cycle. Here, design recommendations were given for the ideal fibre embedding with FIMABOND.

1 INTRODUCTION

In the recent years, lightweight materials and especially fibre-reinforced plastics gain relevance, because of ecological and economic reasons. On the ecological side, emissions have detrimental effects on the environment and can be saved. On the economical side, fuel costs can be reduced and save money over the whole life cycle.

Two main resin systems are predominant in fibre reinforced plastics, which are thermosets and thermoplastics. Thermosets are tight cross-linked chains. They usually have low viscosities, which lead to a high degree of fibre impregnation and therefore higher mechanical properties. Thermoplastics are meltable, wherefore thermoplastics are able to change its shape several times after heating-up. Moreover, thermoplastics are also able for welding processes. But in contrast to thermoplastics, thermosets are not weldable, because the curing reaction by crosslinking is already finished and is not able to go backwards [1].

The state of science describes a few investigations to combine thermosets with thermoplastic surfaces to enable thermosets for welding [2]. One challenge is the avoidance of thermal-induced degradation, which leads to a reduction of the mechanical strengths, but there are method to reduce or avoid these degradations [3]. Many investigations were done in this field by the TU Delft [4]. Usually, thermosets and thermoplastics have limited adhesion forces to each other, when both systems were co-bonded or co-cured. In previous studies, computer-aided methods were developed for PVDF and a multicomponent epoxy resin, which describe the bonding mechanism and the adhesion forces on an atomistic level [5]. Therefore, an additional woven fabric can be used as an interlayer to improve the mechanical properties beside the adhesion forces [6]. The improvement results from the warp and weft yarns of the woven fabric, which continuously change the resin side and act as a form closure. In total, two different bonding

mechanisms exist (adhesion forces between the resin systems and textile form closure between the textile and each resin system) with two crucial interface strengths, which decide about the overall performance of the composite (Fig. 1).

Figure 1: Main principle: Hybrid resin composite with a woven fabric interlayer

This study deals with the fibre-resin-interface, which is heavily dependent by the fibre sizing. Typically, the fibre sizing is tailored either on thermoplastics or on thermosets. Hybrid resin composites require a fibre sizing with good interfacial shear strengths to both resin systems. Therefore, the single fibre pull-out test was used to choose the ideal fibre sizing for the use in hybrid resin composites [7]. Further supporting tests were done for the optimization of the main test setup, especially for embedding the fibre material.

2 MATERIALS AND ITS CHARACTERISATION

In the beginning of the study, fibre and resin materials need to be determined, because of the high amount of available products on the market. The overall objective is an innovative semi-finished product with thermoset as well as thermoplastic resin for high-performance applications. Therefore, HT-carbon (HT) fibres were chosen, because of their high specific tensile strength. Teijin Carbon Europe GmbH offers HT-carbon fibre bundles with three different surface treatments. The type HTS40 consists of the polyurethane surface treatment (F13). The further development of the fibre with slightly increased mechanical properties, HTS45, consists of an epoxy (E23) or thermoplastic (P12) fibre sizing. The tensile strengths of the fibres were determined by FAVIMAT+, which is the same testing device and used for the fibre pull-out tests. Additionally, a second testing device, an Diastron LEX810, was used as well. A clamping length of 20 mm and a testing speed of 2.0 mm/min was used for both testing devices. Overall, 25 single tensile tests were done with the FAVIMAT+ and 15 single tensile tests were done with the Diastron LEX810. The tensile strength of the single carbon fibre is important to know, because it needs to be higher than the tensile strength, which were achieved in the pull-out tests (Equation 1). Otherwise, the fibre would break before it would be pulled out of the thermoplastic resin. If so, the embedding length of the fibre needs to be decreased to avoid premature fibre breakage.

$$F_{CF} > F_{pull-out} \quad (1)$$

The results of the fibre tensile tests are shown in table 1. It can be clearly seen, that both testing units show similar results.

Carbon fibre Tenax-E HTS45	FAVIMAT+	Diastron LEX810
Tensile strength [cN]	15.27	16.00
Elongation [%]	1.84	2.09
Ultimate stress [GPa]	4.16	4.32
Young's modulus [GPa]	215.34	204.39
Fibre diameter [μm]	6.84	6.89

Table 1: Result of the fibre tensile test: Tenax-E HTS45

Regarding the resin systems, several thermoplastics were chosen. The thermoplastics can be subdivided into semi-crystalline, technical thermoplastic polyamide 6 (PA 6) and polyvinylidene fluoride (PVDF) and amorphous high-performance thermoplastic polyetherimide (PEI). The polyamide was supplied by BASF SE and has the brand name Ultramid B27 03. The PVDF in this study was supplied by Arkema and has the brand name Kynar 720. And finally, the PEI was supplied by Sabic with the brand name ULTEM 1000.

To evaluate the ideal embedding conditions for the fibre into the thermoplastic material, thermal analysis has to be done for each material before the fibre embedding and the pull-out test. It has to be ensured, that the thermoplastic resin has a low viscosity. Otherwise, a high viscosity resin hinders the fibre of getting into the resin material.

The rheometer AR2000 by TA Instruments was used to measure the complex viscosity of the thermoplastics. Both materials were heated up over the melting temperature, respectively glass transition temperature, and afterwards cooled down to 180 °C. Then, the measurements were started with a frequency of 5 Hz to 300 °C. The results for PVDF and PA 6 were shown in figure 2.

Figure 2: Complex viscosity in dependence on the temperature between 180 °C and 300 °C

The results for PVDF and PA 6 show a different behaviour to each other. After the PA 6 has reached its melting point (220 °C), a strong drop in the complex viscosity occurred. Then, the complex viscosity continuously and slowly decreases. The PVDF has a glass transition temperature of 177 °C and has a similar continuous decrement. But after 270 °C, a further drop in the complex viscosity took place. At a temperature of 300 °C, the complex viscosity for PVDF is lower than 400 Pa s, which seems to be an appropriate viscosity for fibre embedding. Regarding the PA 6, a complex viscosity lower than 400 Pa s was already achieved with a temperature of 235 °C, but the fibre embedding was done with a temperature of 250 °C. This thermal analysis shows the different thermoplastic behaviour. PEI, the third thermoplastic material, has a completely other behaviour: With a glass transition temperature of 217 °C, the viscosity of the material was still high and not practicable for fibre embedding. The temperature was increased up to 400 °C, which represented a proper viscosity for the use in FIMABOND. In other words, the temperature, which was used in fibre embedding, was over 180 °C higher than the glass transition temperature of PEI. Finally, the importance of a thermal analysis was shown using the material examples of PA 6, PVDF and PEI.

3 FIBER EMBEDDING WITH FIMABOND

The embedding of the carbon fibres was done with the FIMABOND supplied by Textechno H. Stein GmbH & Co. KG. In a first step, the single fibre was put into a pipe, which sucks the fibre for the embedding process. The thermoplastic granulate was laid on an aluminium pan, which was put on the heating unit inside the FIMABOND. With this device, the embedding speed and the embedding depth can be individually set. In the first tests, the speed was set to 0.8 mm/min and the depth was set to 0.6 mm. Optionally, nitrogen in the embedding atmosphere can be used as well. An exemplary cycle for the fiber embedding is shown in figure 3. Here, it can be noticed, that melting of the thermoplastic materials need most of the time of the whole cycle.

Figure 3: Typical embedding cycle for PVDF

Additionally, a camera system is implemented in FIMABOND. It is necessary for the fibre embedding, because the first dipping has to be manually done. The camera system supports due to the localization of the top of the melted thermoplastic material. It is shown in picture 2 with the green line and the red dot (figure 4). After reaching the first contact between fibre and resin, the automatic mode starts and penetrates the fibre into the thermoplastic material up to the embedding depth.

Figure 4: Three steps during fibre embedding: 1. Melting 2. Fibre embedding 3. Cooling

4 QUALITY ASSURANCE WITH X-RAY MICROSCOPE

The embedding device FIMABOND is responsible for the fibre embedding into the melted resin material. Due to the camera system, the surface can be observed, but inside the thermoplastic material, no information is given by the device. Here, scans of an x-ray microscope (XRM) can help to evaluate the quality of the embedded fibres in the resin. The scans were done with the 'Xradia 520 Versa', which was supplied by Carl Zeiss. Several scans were done for the different thermoplastic materials and exemplary figures are presented in figure 5.

By scanning the whole FIMABOND specimen, some obvious deviations catch the eye. At first, foreign particles, like metallic particles, were found inside the thermoplastic materials. Furthermore, many pores, partial bigger bubbles, were noticed as well. By using a closer look inside the specimen with a resolution of 1.0 μm , several further observations can be done. The thermoplastic surface is not smooth. In the area, where the fibre stabbed into the thermoplastic material, a shape like a drop developed on the surface. Furthermore, it can be seen with a higher resolution, that the fibre was deflected by a pore, which led to an oblique fibre in the specimen. Additionally, the real embedding length differed sometimes in comparison to the target depth. With the highest achievable resolution of 0.5 μm , interesting observations regarding the fibre-resin-interface were noticed. Here, a small gap between the fibre and the thermoplastic material of 1.8 μm was found. This mistake would completely lead to an adulterated result by the pull-out test.

Figure 5: Deviation in ideal fibre embedding

All these mistakes can be avoided, when the embedding process is wisely designed. Because some of these deviations result from other deviations, general design recommendations were done:

- Be clear about the fibre's tensile strength, which influence the embedding depth
- Use nitrogen as atmospheric gas in FIMABOND
- Use a higher temperature to decrease the viscosity of the thermoplastic material to lighten the fibre penetration
- Use sufficient time in the holding phase (1) of isothermal melting temperature to homogenize the melted thermoplastic material
- Use lower cooling rates, because the quality of the specimens will be improved
- Use lower embedding speeds

A good prearrangement takes time but reflects a good test implementation of a very powerful testing device. Even if no quantitative relationships between the process and embedding conditions are not focused in this study, the general recommendation help the investigator to raise the quality of embedded fibres with the FIMABOND.

5 FIBRE PULL-OUT TEST WITH FAVIMAT+

The pull-out test was done with the test device FAVIMAT+ supplied by Textechno H. Stein GmbH & Co. KG as well. Force-displacement-diagrams are the result, which describe the mechanical characteristics during the pull-out test (Fig. 3).

The first eye-catching point in the graph is F_d . Here, the gradient becomes lower. F_d is the debonding force, which shows the first failure between the fibre and resin. The crack propagates along the fibre-resin-interface. When the crack is propagated along the whole embedded fibre, the second point of interest is achieved, which characterizes the maximum force F_{max} . The force immediately drops to the minimum force F_b . From this point up to the end of the pull-out test, just friction between the fibre and resin acts as occurring force. The variable l_e represents the embedding length l_e [8].

Especially, when the force-displacement-diagram do not represent this typical behavior, the quality of the embedded specimens shall be controlled. Additionally, the embedding length, which is displayed in the force-displacement-diagram has to be equal with the target embedding length, which was set in

the FIMABOND. Otherwise, something does not work well during the pull-out test and is an evidence for testing the quality of the specimens.

Figure 3: Exemplary force-displacement-diagram of a single fiber pull-out test [8]

6 SUMMARY AND OUTLOOK

In this study, the prearrangements for the fibre pull-out test were presented by using the testing devices of Textechno H. Stein GmbH & Co. KG, which are called FIMABOND and FAVIMAT+. Due to these test devices, simple and automatic methods are available on the market to get information about the fibre-resin-properties. The study has shown simple pretests, like the determination of carbon fiber's tensile strength or the thermal analysis, which influence the process parameters during fibre embedding and has to be known by the user. An x-ray microscope has been used to identify possible defects of embedded fibres in different thermoplastic materials, when the embedding conditions were not chosen well. Simple and obvious defects like metallic particles have been clearly noticed. More complicated defects like the missing bonding between the fibre and the resin material, which can just be observed with a high resolution of 0.5 μm , are more challenging to detect, because it has a great influence within the pull-out test. To avoid the presented deviations, process recommendations for fibre embedding were presented. It is vitally important to calculate and use enough time for the fibre embedding, for example while melting the thermoplastic material or cooling the material. This study just exemplarily presented occurring defects, when using inappropriate embedding parameters, which would lead to adulterated results after the pull-out test. In future work, the general process recommendations have to be categorized regarding the different materials. Additionally, quantitative specifications need to be done to evaluate the influence of each defect within the pull-out test.

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